

Investigating the Correlation Between Input Length and Error-to-Signal Loss in WaveNet on an End-To-End Audio Generation Task

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Abstract

This paper investigates the correlation between input length and error-to-signal ratio loss in WaveNet, a deep generative model that works on the raw audio domain, on an end-to-end audio generation task. The task involves training WaveNet with a dataset of paired data, where each pair consists of a clean, undistorted signal and a distorted signal where a Tube Screamer pedal is applied. Our results indicate that the input length significantly affects the performance of WaveNet, with longer input lengths leading to lower error-to-signal ratio losses. This suggests that the model is able to make more accurate predictions when trained on longer audio signals. This study contributes to the field of audio signal processing by presenting a broader understanding of WaveNet’s sensitivity on input length in audio generation tasks and highlights the need for further research in this area.

Keywords — *WaveNet, Distortion, Audio Generation, Deep Learning, Signal Processing, Sensitivity*

1 Introduction

Deep learning has revolutionized many fields and had emerged into the society with its practical applications in various fields. The music industry is one of the fields that deep learning has greatly impacted, with hundreds of new products now incorporating deep learning algorithms. One particular area that attracted recent AI research is Digital Signal Processing, where hundreds of new amplifier, pedal, and tone modellers are being built.

One of the most notable architectures in this domain is WaveNet, a deep generative model of raw audio waveforms developed by van den Oord et al. [9]. WaveNet has shown remarkable performance in tasks such as speech synthesis and music generation. One interesting aspect of WaveNet is that it operates in the raw audio domain, where the input to the model is the raw audio signal. Instead of relying on intermediate representations such as spectrograms, WaveNet is an end-to-end approach to generating waveforms [9].

The audio generation task in this study involves training WaveNet with a dataset of paired data, where each pair consists of a clean, undistorted signal and a signal distorted by a Tube Screamer. The Tube Screamer, a popular guitar effect pedal, provides a distortion effect that adds complexity to the audio signal. By training WaveNet on this dataset, we aim to understand how the model responds to different input lengths and how this affects the error-to-signal ratio loss and computational complexity.

In this paper, we investigate the correlation between input length and error-to-signal ratio loss in WaveNet on an end-to-end audio generation task. We train WaveNet with various input lengths and analyze the resulting loss. Our goal is to gain a deeper understanding of WaveNet’s sensitivity to input length, which could help in optimizing its performance and efficiency.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 1.1 reviews related work, Section 2 provides background knowledge on deep learning and signal processing, Section 3 describes our methodology, Section 4 presents our results, Section 5 discusses these results and their implications, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

1.1 Related Work

The application of deep learning techniques in audio signal processing has been a topic of interest in recent years. In the music industry, Deep Learning attracted many companies to build AI modellers of guitar amplifiers, pedals, and tones. One recent example is the company NeuralDSP, which has multiple modeller plugins and a stomp pedal powered by neural networks [1].

WaveNet, a deep generative model of raw audio waveforms, has been at the forefront of this research due to its ability to generate high-quality audio. Van den Oord et al. [9] introduced WaveNet and demonstrated its effectiveness in tasks such as text to speech synthesis and music generation. Their work laid the foundation for the use of WaveNet in audio signal processing, but did not extensively explore the impact of the network in modelling electric guitar effects.

Several studies have investigated and researched ways to model guitar amplifiers using Deep Learning. For instance, Wright et al. [10] used a modified WaveNet architecture and a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) model trained on a dataset of audio recordings of three distortion pedals. Their experiments show that WaveNet outperforms RNNs in accuracy, but the computation time is much slower [10].

Other studies investigated the the sensitivity of deep learning models to the input and hyperparameters. For instance, Zhang et al. [12] examined the sensitivity of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to various factors such as input representation, hyperparameters, and activation functions in image classification tasks. However, the sensitivity of WaveNet to input length in audio generation tasks remains less explored.

In terms of audio distortion, the work of Pakarinen et al. [5] provides a comprehensive review of methods for digital simulation of guitar distortion circuits, including the Tube Screamer. Their work provides valuable insights into the characteristics of distorted audio signals, but does not consider the application of deep learning models for processing these signals.

This study aims to fill these gaps by investigating the correlation between input length and error-to-signal ratio loss in WaveNet on an end-to-end audio generation task. By training WaveNet on a dataset of clean and Tube Screamer distorted signals, we hope to shed light on the sensitivity of WaveNet in response to input length.

2 Background Knowledge

2.1 Deep Learning

Deep learning is a subfield of machine learning that focuses on mathematical models inspired by the structure and function of the brain, called artificial neural networks. These algorithms are designed to learn from large amounts of data, and have been successful in various tasks, including image recognition, natural language processing, and audio signal processing [7].

Deep learning models are composed of multiple layers of neurons, or nodes, each of which performs a basic computation on the data. Typically, neural networks compose of 3 main parts: the input layer, the hidden layers, and the output layer. The data is fed into the input layer, which passes it to the hidden layers where various neurons perform computations on the data, and it is then passed to the output layer. Each layer has activation functions that can add non linearity using non-linear operations such as ReLU, sigmoid, or tanh. The output of one layer serves as the input to the next, allowing the model to learn complex, hierarchical representations of the data. This layered architecture enables deep learning models to automatically extract useful features from raw data, eliminating the need for manual feature engineering which is one of the deficiencies of traditional machine learning techniques.

Deep learning has been particularly successful in tasks that involve high-dimensional, unstructured data, such as images, text, and audio [7]. By learning directly from raw data, deep learning models can capture intricate structures and patterns that would be difficult to model with traditional machine learning techniques.

Neural networks work by iteratively passing the data through its layers in a process called "forward propagation", calculating the loss from the labels and the output, then optimizing the weights of each layer in a backwards fashion through a process called "Back propagation". Back propagation optimizes the weights of a layer by simply taking a step in the negative direction of the gradient of the loss function. By applying the forward propagation and back propagation many times on the training dataset, the neural network learns the data and can accurately model it.

It is worth to note that neural networks are often referred to as universal function approximators [3]. This term originates from the Universal Approximation Theorem, which states that a feed-forward network with a single hidden layer containing a finite number of neurons can approximate continuous functions on compact subsets of real numbers, under mild assumptions on the activation function. The power of neural networks lies in their ability to model complex, non-linear relationships directly from data, without the need for explicit programming. By optimizing the weights and biases during the training process, neural networks learn to approximate the underlying function that maps inputs to outputs in the given data [3]. This makes them highly versatile and applicable to a wide range of tasks, from image recognition to natural language processing and audio signal processing. In this study, the underlying function that maps the input signal to the output signal is simply the distortion function that the Ibanez Tube Screamer Mini pedal applies.

2.2 Distortion Effect

Audio signal processing involves the analysis, synthesis, and modification of sound waves. It is a field that intertwines elements from acoustics, electronics, and computer science. Audio signal processing techniques are used in a wide range of applications and are widely used in guitar amplification modellers.

Distortion is one of the effects used in audio signal processing. Distortion is essentially a decibel boost, but some types of distortion works differently in terms of clipping the input signal. Although distortion increases the amplitude of audio signals, the frequency remains unchanged.

Mathematically, a distortion function transforms a wave by increasing its amplitude and clipping the wave over some threshold. Given a signal with data points x_i , the output of a gain effect could be represented with:

$$y_i = g(x_i) = \alpha f(x_i) + (1 - \alpha)x_i \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is the weight of the distortion effect, f is the nonlinear distortion effect, and g is the sum of the clean and distorted signal. Modelling distortion functions tries to approximate the function f with respect to α [4].

A distortion effect could be soft-clipping or hard-clipping. Hard clipping refers to cutting the signal roughly over some amplitude threshold, and soft clipping refers to cutting the signal by smoothening over some amplitude threshold [4]. As such, the nonlinear distortion effect f could be represented with:

$$f(x_i) = \lambda(\sigma(x_i, \gamma)) \quad (2)$$

where $\lambda : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [-\theta_c, \theta_c]$ is a clipping function and θ_c is the clipping threshold. The function $\sigma(x_i, \gamma) = 10^{\frac{\gamma}{20}} x_i$ applies the gain to the audio signal, effectively increasing or decreasing its amplitude. γ controls the gain amount in decibels (dB) [4].

Hard-clipping could be achieved by limiting the gain amplification of signal for data points between some threshold $[-\theta_c, \theta_c]$, and letting the data points above or below the thresholds to have value of the threshold [4]:

$$\lambda_{hc}(\sigma(x_i, \gamma)) = \begin{cases} \sigma(x_i, \gamma) & \text{if } |\sigma(x_i, \gamma)| \leq \theta_c \\ \text{sgn}(\sigma(x_i, \gamma)) \cdot \theta_c & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Soft-clipping distortion functions smoothen the edges while applying gain. There are various types of soft-clipping distortion functions, a common one being [4]:

$$\lambda_{sc}(\sigma(x_i, \gamma)) = \begin{cases} \sigma(x_i, \gamma), & \text{if } |\sigma(x_i, \gamma)| \leq \theta_c \\ \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan(\gamma x_i) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Tube screamer pedal or other distortion pedals use such functions and circuit elements such as diodes and transistors to add gain to the input signal, making it sound harsher.

2.3 Tube Screamer Distortion

The Tube Screamer is a popular guitar effect pedal that provides a distortion effect. It works by clipping the audio signal, which adds harmonics and changes the waveform. This distortion effect is often used in music to add richness and complexity to the sound.

The Tube Screamer is known for its smooth, warm distortion tone, which is achieved by soft clipping the audio signal. This results in a waveform that retains more of its original shape, compared to hard clipping, which produces a more harsh and aggressive distortion. The Tube Screamer also includes a tone control circuit, which allows the user to adjust the balance of high and low frequencies in the distorted signal.

In this study, we use the Tube Screamer distortion as a way to add complexity to our audio signals and challenge the WaveNet model. By training the model on both clean and distorted signals, we aim to investigate how the model adapts to the added complexity and how this affects its performance.

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset

The dataset consists of paired audio signals, each pair containing a clean, undistorted signal and a signal distorted by an Ibanez Tube Screamer. The paired data is a 2-tuple $(\mathbf{x}, f(\mathbf{x}))$, where f is the corresponding distortion function [11]. The clean, undistorted signal is collected from the BOSS-Katana amplifier using an audio interface, and then sampled with a sampling rate of 44100 Hz. It is represented as a vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^t$ with the values indicating the amplitude of the signal. The pedal is placed before the amplifier, and when engaged, it produces the distortion effect. The distorted signal is collected with the same equipment, and is represented as a vector $f(\mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^t$.

In this study, we used a specific set of equipment for data collection to ensure the consistency and quality of the audio signals. As detailed in Table 1, this included a BOSS Katana MKII 50 watts amplifier and its built-in audio interface, a Macbook M2 air computer, an Ibanez Tube Screamer Mini pedal powered with a 9 watts DC adapter, and GarageBand as the Digital Audio Workstation (DAW). The amplifier had all its knobs at middle, providing no boost or cut in any frequencies of the sound, with no reverb or any other time-based effects active. The knobs on the Tube Screamer pedal were also set to 12 to not boost or cut any frequency and to maintain a clean and consistent audio signal. The guitar used in this experiment is an Epiphone 60's Les Paul model with the stock ProBucker pickups. All audio signals were recorded using the clean channel of the amplifier and the Tube Screamer pedal, with no additional plugins or effects from the DAW. This setup allowed us to focus on the effect of the Tube Screamer distortion and the input length on the performance of the WaveNet model.

Equipment	Model	Notes
Amplifier	BOSS-Katana MKII 50 W	The amp had EQ knobs all at 12 o clock with no reverb and delay, using the clean channel of the amplifier.
Audio Interface	BOSS-Katana MKII-50 W built-in interface	
Computer	Macbook M2 air	macOS 12.5
Pedal	Ibanez Tube Screamer Mini, powered with a 9 W DC adapter	The pedal had knobs all at 12 o clock
Electric Guitar	Epiphone 60's Les Paul	The guitar featured its original ProBucker 2, and 3 [2]
DAW	GarageBand	No plugins and effects, only the Katana source.

Table 1: List of equipment used in data collection.

The collected audio signals are of varying lengths, including 20 seconds, 50 seconds, 90 seconds, and 180 seconds. Each input length features 4 instances of audio recordings. The WaveNet is trained on each of the 4 instances and the mean loss is recorded to be more accurate. The dataset used in this study is publicly available and can be accessed from the GitHub repository at <https://github.com/egehurturk/TNet>. We encourage other researchers to utilize this dataset for further investigation and to reproduce our results.

The recordings are converted into Mono from Stereo and normalized to ensure faster and stable training.

The dataset was split into training, validation, and test sets, with 60% of the data used for training, 20% for validation, and 20% for testing. Each data split was standardized by subtracting the mean of the split from the values and dividing by the standard deviation. This ensured normalization and provided a faster training time.

3.2 WaveNet

WaveNet is an autoregressive and a probabilistic deep neural network for generating raw audio waveforms developed by van den Oord et al. [9]. It is a type of convolutional neural network (CNN) that operates directly on the raw audio waveform, and is capable of generating high-quality audio. WaveNet is particularly successful in text to speech generation, yielding state-of-the-art performances.

We decided to utilize WaveNet in modelling the Tube Screamer pedal due to its capabilities as an end-to-end approach for generating raw audio that works on raw audio waveform instead of spectrograms or other intermediate results [9].

3.2.1 End-to-end Audio Generation

The primary concept driving WaveNet is the modeling of the conditional probability of the subsequent sample in the audio waveform, given the preceding samples. This approach is a departure from conventional methods of audio generation, which typically involve transforming the audio signal into a different domain, such as the frequency domain, and modeling the transformed signal.

Traditional methods often involve a two-step process: feature extraction and then modeling. In the feature extraction step, some characteristics or features are extracted from the raw audio signal, such as spectral features or cepstral features. These features are then used as input to a model, such as a Hidden Markov Model or a Gaussian Mixture Model, which generates the audio signal.

In contrast, WaveNet operates directly on the raw audio waveform, eliminating the need for feature extraction. This end-to-end approach has several advantages. First, it avoids the information loss that can

occur during feature extraction. Second, it allows the model to learn and exploit any structure or patterns in the raw audio signal that may not be captured by the extracted features.

Furthermore, by modeling the conditional probability of the next sample, WaveNet is able to generate audio one sample at a time. This allows it to generate audio of any length, and to start generating audio as soon as it has processed the first few samples. Using dilated convolutional layers further increases its receptive layer, which results in coherent and longer generated audio [9].

Figure 1: The WaveNet architecture.

3.2.2 Architecture

WaveNet models the joint probability of a waveform $\mathbf{x}$ with a stack of dilated causal convolutional layers, where each layer corresponds to a different time scale. The joint probability is decomposed into a product of conditional probabilities as:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \prod_{t=1}^T p(x_t | x_1, \dots, x_{t-1}) \quad (5)$$

In Equation 5, each term $p(x_t | x_1, \dots, x_{t-1})$ represents the conditional probability of x_t given the previous samples $x_1, \dots, x_{t-1}$. When a sample is generated, it is fed back into the network to be used in predicting the next sample.

The dilated causal convolution blocks allows the model to capture both short-term and long-term dependencies in the audio signal. Using dilations increases the receptive field while requiring few layers. This increases computational efficiency and ensures the consistency of input resolution throughout the network. The authors of WaveNet suggest doubling the dilation for every layer up to a limit and repeating, as the exponential increase in dilation rate results in an exponential increase in receptive field [9].

Each convolution layer in WaveNet is followed by a gated activation unit, which is a combination of a tanh and a sigmoid activation function:

$$\mathbf{z} = \tanh(W_{f,k} * \mathbf{x}) \odot \sigma(W_{g,k} * \mathbf{x}), \quad (6)$$

where $*$ is the convolution operation, $\odot$ is the element-wise multiplication, σ is the sigmoid function $\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$, k denotes the layer index, f and g denote the filter and gate, and W denotes the convolution filter. The paper states that the gated activation unit produced better results than the ReLU function, and allowed the network to model complex, non-linear relationships in the audio signal [9].

The skip connections and residuals from the stack of dilated causal convolutional layers pass through a ReLU activation function, followed by a 1x1 convolution block, a ReLU activation function, a 1x1 convolution block, and a softmax layer, as can be seen in Figure 1. The softmax layer discretizes the audio signal into a set of possible values, and predicts the probability of each value. The architecture of the network is shown in Figure 1.

3.3 Training

The WaveNet model was trained on the paired audio signals, with the clean signal as the input and the distorted signal as the target. The model was trained to minimize the error-to-signal ratio loss, which measures the difference between the predicted and target signals:

$$\epsilon_{\text{ESR}} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |y_p(n) - \hat{y}_p(n)|^2}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |y_p(n)|^2} \quad (7)$$

where $y_p(n)$ is the output (i.e., ground truth) with the pre-emphasis filter applied, and $\hat{y}_p(n)$ is the predicted output with the pre-emphasis filter applied. According to Wright et al., the high-pass pre-emphasis filter boosts the mid and high frequencies which helps the network to perform better [10]. Without applying the high-pass pre-emphasis filter, the results from Wright et al. indicates audible deformations in the mid frequencies [10]. The pre-emphasis filter used is:

$$H(z) = 1 - 0.95z^{-1} \quad (8)$$

The model was trained with a T4 GPU, hosted in Google Colaboratory. We trained the network 4 times for each of the input length, and monitored the error-to-signal-ratio loss in each trial. The hyperparameters were constant throughout the training, and are listed in Table 2.

Parameter	Value
sample_rate	44.1 kHz
normalize	True
num_channels	4
dilation_depth	9
num_repeat	2
kernel_size	3
batch_size	64
learning_rate	3e-3
epochs	10000

Table 2: Training hyperparameters for the WaveNet model.

The training was performed using the Adam optimizer [6], a popular optimization algorithm for deep learning models. Adam was chosen for its efficiency and good performance in practice. The learning rate was set to $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$, which provided a good balance between convergence speed and stability. A batch size of 64 was used to split the training dataset into smaller batches. This batch size was chosen to balance the computational efficiency and the quality of the gradient estimate.

The training process was carried out for 10000 epochs, where an epoch is one complete pass through the entire batch. This number of epochs was chosen to allow the model to sufficiently learn the underlying patterns in the data, without overfitting.

During the training process, the model’s performance was evaluated on a validation set, which is a separate set of data not used in training. After each epoch, the validation error was computed and monitored. The monitored losses were saved as checkpoints and loaded into TensorBoard for visualization.

4 Results

Our experiments yielded significant findings regarding the correlation between input length and error-to-signal ratio loss in WaveNet on an end-to-end audio generation task.

4.1 Error-to-Signal Ratio Loss

Table 3 shows the error-to-signal ratio loss for different input lengths.

Input Length	E2S				Mean E2S	
	<i>Model 1</i>	<i>Model 2</i>	<i>Model 3</i>	<i>Model 4</i>	<i>No Filter</i>	<i>With Pre-emphasis Filter</i>
20	0.8660	1.1660	0.5260	0.8110	0.8423	0.8324158
50	0.2596	0.1900	0.1813	0.1720	0.2007	0.1934102
90	0.06444	0.1113	0.07772	0.06613	0.07991	0.0720231

Table 3: Error to signal values for different trainings and mean errors

The table presents the Error-to-Signal (E2S) ratio values obtained from four different trained WaveNet models for each of three different input lengths (20, 50, and 90 seconds). The E2S ratio is a measure of the difference between the predicted and target signals, with a lower value indicating a closer match to the target signal.

For each input length, the E2S values from the four training runs are listed, followed by the mean E2S values calculated with and without a pre-emphasis filter. The pre-emphasis filter is a processing step used to balance the frequency spectrum by increasing the amplitude of high-frequency bands and decreasing the amplitude of low-frequency bands [10].

Looking at the 20-second input length, the E2S values range from 0.5260 to 1.1660 across the four training runs. The mean E2S value is $\mu = 0.8423$ without the pre-emphasis filter and slightly lower at $\mu = 0.8422753$ with the filter.

For the 50-second input length, the E2S values are noticeably lower, ranging from 0.1720 to 0.2596. Each second of the input audio adds 44100 data points (the audios are sampled with a frequency of $44.1kHz$), which helps WaveNet in training. The mean E2S value is $\mu = 0.2007$ without the filter and slightly higher at $\mu = 0.2007201$ with the filter. This indicates that the model performs better with a longer input length.

Finally, for the 90-second input length, the E2S values are even lower, ranging from 0.06444 to 0.1113. The mean E2S value is $\mu = 0.07991$ without the filter. This suggests that the model performs best with this input length.

These results suggest that the input length significantly affects the performance of the model, with longer input lengths leading to lower E2S values.

The figures 2, 3, 4 shows the difference between the model’s output and the real output for each input length. It is evident that, as the input length increases, the error significantly decreases, and the difference between the actual output and the predicted decreases.

Figure 2: The Difference in Audio Signals in a 20-second Sample

Figure 3: The Difference in Audio Signals in a 50-second Sample

Figure 4: The Difference in Audio Signals in a 90-second Sample

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The objective of the correlation analysis was to investigate the relationship between the input length and the error-to-signal (E2S) ratio loss in WaveNet. The input length refers to the duration of the audio signals used to train the model, while the E2S ratio loss is a measure of the difference between the predicted and target signals, with a lower value indicating a closer match to the target signal.

The variables of interest were thus the input length (independent variable) and the mean E2S ratio loss (dependent variable). We hypothesized that there would be a significant correlation between these two variables, with longer input lengths leading to lower E2S values. Our hypothesis was based on the fact that deep learning models, particularly neural networks, generally approximate functions better when there are more data, but we also tried to investigate overfitting as well. This hypothesis was also based on the assumption that longer audio signals contain more information, which could potentially allow the model to make more accurate predictions.

To test this hypothesis, we used Pearson’s correlation coefficient, a statistical measure that measures the correlation between two sets of data. Pearson’s correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1, with -1 indicating a perfect negative correlation, 1 indicating a perfect positive correlation, and 0 indicating no correlation [8]. Figure 5 shows the correlation between input length and E2S loss.

The results of the correlation analysis revealed a strong negative correlation between input length and the E2S ratio loss. The correlation coefficient was -0.8334 , indicating a strong negative relationship. This indicates that as the input length increases, the E2S ratio loss decreases.

This finding supports our hypothesis and suggests that the input length significantly affects the performance of WaveNet. Longer input lengths appear to lead to lower E2S values, suggesting that the model is able to make more accurate predictions when trained on longer audio signals. This could be due to the increased information content in longer signals, which may provide the model with more context for making predictions.

However, it’s important to note that correlation does not imply causation. While our results suggest a strong relationship between input length and E2S ratio loss, further research is needed to determine whether and how the input length directly influences the model’s performance. It’s also possible that other factors, such as the complexity of the audio signal or the specific characteristics of the training data, could be influencing the E2S ratio loss.

Figure 5: E2S Loss VS Input Length

5 Discussion

5.1 Limitations

While our study provides important findings, it is not without limitations. First, our dataset consisted of audio signals distorted by a Tube Screamer. While this added complexity to the audio signals, it may limit the generalizability of our findings to other types of audio signals. The Tube Screamer distortion has specific characteristics that may not be representative of other types of audio distortions, such as boosting mid frequencies. To support other distortion based effects, the model should be trained on an audio sample with the effect and without.

Second, the analysis includes few specific input lengths. While these lengths provided a range of data for analysis, they do not cover all possible input lengths. Therefore, our findings may not fully capture the sensitivity of WaveNet to input length. Further research is needed to explore a wider range of input lengths and to confirm our findings. In addition, more data with higher input lengths should be considered to investigate overfitting in WaveNet.

Lastly, while collecting audio samples from the amplifier, our research did not utilize signal splitter that would allow a direct recording of both clean and distorted signal, but instead did 2 recordings – one for the clean and one for the distorted. This caused minor differences between the audio recordings, and these differences could contribute to E2S loss. Utilizing signal splitter or any other device that would allow for direct recording of clean and distorted signal at the same time would have more accurate results.

5.2 Improvements and Future Work

Future research could improve upon our study in several ways. First, researchers could use a more diverse dataset, including audio signals distorted by different types of effects. This would help to generalize the findings to a wider range of audio signals. By understanding how WaveNet performs with different types of distortions, we can gain a more comprehensive understanding of its capabilities and limitations.

Second, researchers could investigate a wider range of input lengths to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the sensitivity of WaveNet to input length. This could involve not only longer input lengths, but also shorter ones. By exploring this aspect further, we can better understand the trade-offs between input length and model performance, which could inform the design and application of WaveNet and other deep learning models in audio signal processing.

6 Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the sensitivity of WaveNet, a deep generative model of raw audio waveforms, to the length of the input signal in an end-to-end audio generation task. Our findings suggest that the input length significantly affects the performance of WaveNet, with longer input lengths leading to lower error-to-signal ratio losses. This suggests that the model is able to make more accurate predictions when trained on longer audio signals.

Our correlation analysis further confirmed this relationship, revealing a strong negative correlation between input length and error-to-signal ratio loss. This finding contributes to the broader understanding of how input length affects the performance of deep learning models in audio signal processing.

While our study provides valuable insights, it also highlights the need for further research. Future studies could explore a wider range of input lengths, use a more diverse dataset, and investigate other factors that could influence the performance of WaveNet. By continuing to explore these issues, we can further improve the performance of WaveNet and other deep learning models in audio signal processing, and contribute to the development of high-quality, efficient, and effective audio generation systems.

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A Appendix

The source code for this research along with the dataset used to train WaveNet is publicly available in the GitHub repository <https://github.com/egehurturk/TSNet>.